

Reading and Readability in Complex Writing Systems

Basel, 25th-26th May 2014

eikones'

NFS Bildkritik
NCCR Iconic Criticism

UNI
BASEL

FNSNF
FONDS NATIONAL SUISSE
SCHWEIZERISCHER NATIONALFONDS
FONDO NAZIONALE SVIZZERO
SWISS NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

Sunday, May 25th 2014

eikones Forum, Rheinsprung 11

- 9.00-9.15 Greetings, Andréas Stauder (Basel)
Introduction, Antonio Loprieno (Basel)
- 9.15-10.15 Die Sprache der Schrift, Massimiliano Marazzi (Neapel)
- 10.15-11.15 Pragmatic aspects of phonographic and semographic spelling in (cursive) Hieroglyphic-Egyptian texts, Daniel Werning (Berlin)

Coffee break

- 11.30-12.30 The logography-phonography continuum based on Peircean semiotics, Gianni Wan (Beijing)

Lunch, eikones, Rheinsprung 11

- 14.00-15.00 The Use of Determinatives in Hieroglyphic Luwian, Annick Payne (Basel)
- 15.00-16.00 Talking about reading when there are no readers any more: Functional aspects of Egyptian writing, Andréas Stauder (Basel)

Coffee break

- 16.30-17.30 The Readability of Egyptian Hieroglyphs at Esna: A functional approach, David Klotz (Yale/Basel)

19.00 Dinner: Picobello, Blumenrain 12

Monday, May 26th 2014

Universität Basel, Rosshof, Seminarraum Schnitz, Rm. S01

- 9.00-10.00 Reading and readability of iconic, scriptural and para-scriptural information in the process of making the decoration of Ancient Egyptian monuments, Dimitri Laboury (Liège)
- 10.00-11.00 Neural mechanism underlying orthographic processing in normal and dyslexic reading, Urs Maurer (Zurich)

Coffee break

- 11.30-12.30 The Use of Hittite Logogramms, Willemijn Waal (Leiden)

Lunch: Restaurant du Moyen Orient, Petersgraben 15

- 14.00-15.00 On the relationship between character embellishment, object decoration and readability in Chinese paleography from the Eastern Zhou period, Wolfgang Behr (Zurich)
- 15.00-16.00 Reading the Unwritten and Writing the Unspoken: A cognitive study of writing and reading in Classic Maya Culture, Christian Prager (Bonn)

Dept. Altertumswissenschaften, Petersgraben 51, Rm. 306

Coffee break

- 16.30-17.30 Features distinctive of early writing systems reveal the cognitive preadaptations for literacy, Adam Smith (Pennsylvania)

17.30 Conclusion